

STUDIES ON CARBON MONOXIDE AND CARBON MONOXIDE—HYDROGEN MIXTURES UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE: INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE AND GAS PRESSURE

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Results for (a) CO and (b) CO-H₂ mixtures in silent discharge by 3 to 9 kV of 500 cycles, in 100 to 400 mm. showed a maximum pressure reduction (Δp) of about 17%, followed by a steady state. Initial pressure rise and temperature fall decrease Δp in (a) and increase it in (b). Initial Δp corresponds to 'second order reaction' associated with H.CHO formation in (b). 'First order' constants are observed in (a) near the steady state due to dissociation of the suboxide complex and ionic clusters.

The behaviour of carbon monoxide has been studied under silent electric discharge by Brodie (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1873, 21, 245; *Ann. Physik*, 1873, 169, 270; *Ann. chim. Pharm.*, 1873, 169, 270), Berthelot (*Compt. rend.*, 1906, 142, 533; *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1906, viii, 9, 173), Ott (*Ber.*, 1925, 58, 772), Crespi and Lunt (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2052). Formation of CO₂ and the ill defined 'carbon suboxides' has been reported. In the case of CO-H₂ mixtures studied by Losanitsch (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 312), Löb (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3593), Wendt and Evans (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2610) and Koenig and Wenig (*Festschrift 100-Jahr. Bestehen, Tech. Hochschule zu Karlsruhe*, 1925, p. 525), the formation of a number of products amongst them CO₂, H.CHO, H.CO.OH, CH₂OH.CHO etc. has been reported. No attempt, however, appears to have been made, excepting one by Caress and Rideal (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, A, 120, 370) in the case of CO-H₂ interaction, at elucidating the mechanism and kinetics of these reactions. In view of the earlier work of the authors (under publication) a re-examination of the above systems appeared of interest. The influence of temperature and of gas pressure has been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general arrangement of the apparatus and electrical connections are shown in Fig. 1. The apparatus in its essentials consists of an all-glass Siemens' ozoniser O, a manometer M to note the pressure variations and a reservoir R to store the gases, all connected in series. The two stoppers T₁ and T₂, in between the ozoniser and the reservoir, serve the purpose of admitting and regulating the gas to the ozoniser at any desired pressure. The system is connected to a Töpler through two glass stoppers T₃ and T₄, by means of which vacuum could be created in the ozoniser. This last is surrounded with a water jacket which can be heated to any desired temperature.

By connecting T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ to the Töpler vacuum was created inside the whole system. Carbon monoxide, prepared separately by the action of hot concentrated sulphuric acid on oxalic acid and freed from CO₂ or its mixture with H₂, was admitted into the reservoir R through T₄ and the drying tubes A and B containing phosphorus pentoxide and anhydrous calcium chloride respectively. By suitably working the stop-

TABLE I
Carbon monoxide : Influence of initial gas pressure and temperature.

No.	Applied potential (kV).	40°				50°				70°				80°			
		Initial pressure (mm.)	Total fall in pres- sure (mm.)	% Re- duction in pres- sure.	Time reqd. to reach equilib. (min.)	Initial pres- sure (mm.)	Total fall in pres- sure (mm.)	% Re- duction in pres- sure.	Time reqd. to reach equilib. (min.)	Initial pres- sure (mm.)	Total fall in pres- sure (mm.)	% Re- duction in pres- sure.	Time reqd. to reach equilib. (min.)	Initial pres- sure (mm.)	Total fall in pres- sure (mm.)	% Re- duction in pres- sure.	Time reqd. to reach equilib. (min.)
1	4.8	191.0	28.0	14.6	105	188.0	28.5	15.1	150	201.0	30.5	15.1	90	196.0	28.0	14.3	90
2	6.0	257.0	35.0	13.6	165	261.0	36.5	13.9	135	276.5	42.5	15.4	105	261.5	40.5	15.5	75
3	7.2	333.0	44.0	13.6	120	322.5	41.0	12.7	135	333.0	50.5	15.1	120	320.0	47.5	14.9	105
4	8.25	383.5	40.5	10.5	120	394.0	48.5	12.3	120	405.0	57.5	13.6	90	420.0	55.0	15.2	90

In studying the influence of temperature it was not possible to take a constant pressure at different temperatures. The pressure varies between 188-201, 257-276.5, 320-333 and 383.5-420 mm.

TABLE II
Carbon monoxide + hydrogen : Influence of initial gas pressure and temperature.

No.	Applied potential (kV).	30°				50°				70°			
		Initial pressure (mm.)	Total fall in pres- sure (mm.)	% Re- duction in pres- sure.	Time reqd. to reach equilib. (min.)	Initial pres- sure (mm.)	Total fall in pres- sure (mm.)	% Re- duction in pres- sure.	Time reqd. to reach equilib. (min.)	Initial pres- sure (mm.)	Total fall in pres- sure (mm.)	% Re- duction in pres- sure.	Time reqd. to reach equilib. (min.)
1	3.3	145	10.0	6.9	5	140	11.4	8.1	10	143	1.0	0.7	5
2	4.05	193	11.0	5.7	10	186	4.9	2.6	10	196	4.9	2.5	10
3	4.8	256	25.0	9.7	30	260	21.0	8.1	90	280	16.5	5.9	90
4	6.9	374	36.0	9.6	45	383	67.0	17.5	90	386	50.0	12.9	165
5	9.0	516	42.0	8.1	75								

In studying the influence of temperature it was not possible to take a constant pressure at different temperatures. The pressure varies between 140-145, 186-196, 256-280 and 374-386 mm.

TABLE III

Velocity constant of C(O)-H₂ reaction in the initial stage of discharge.

Temp.	Initial pressure (a)	Pressure after 2 min. (a-x)	Pressure after 5 min. (a-x')	Pressure after 10 min. (a-x'')	$k_{(b)mol.} = \frac{1}{at} \times \frac{x}{(a-x)}$		
					$k_2 \text{ min.} \times 10^{-4} \text{min}^{-1}$	$k_5 \text{ min.} \times 10^{-4} \text{min}^{-1}$	$k_{10} \text{ min.} \times 10^{-4} \text{min}^{-1}$
30°	145 mm.	140.8 mm.	135 mm.	135 mm.	10.28	10.22	—
"	193	188.8	183	182	5.762	5.661	3.131
"	256	248.9	239	235	5.572	5.556	3.490
"	374	361.5	344	342	4.623	4.662	2.501
"	516	484.0	479	475	6.407	2.991	1.673
50°	140	139.6	139	138	1.025	1.028	1.035
"	186	185.0	183.5	181.1	1.453	1.464	1.455
"	260	252.0	250	248	6.105	3.077	1.861
"	383	374.5	362.5	358	2.963	2.953	1.823
70°	143	142.5	142	142	0.981	0.985	—
"	196	195.0	193.5	191.1	1.308	1.318	1.308
"	280	276.0	273	270	2.588	2.007	1.322
"	386	376.0	371	369	3.445	2.094	1.193

TABLE IV

Velocity constants (near the equilibrium) of C(O).

Time (mins.)	70°		50°		40°							
	Initial pressure a = 333 mm.	Initial pressure a = 261 mm.	Initial pressure a = 322.5 mm.	Initial pressure a = 394 mm.	Initial pressure a = 191 mm.	Initial pressure a = 257 mm.						
	a-x.	$k_{(a)mol.} \times 10^{-4} \text{min.}^{-1}$	a-x.	$k_{(a)mol.} \times 10^{-4} \text{min.}^{-1}$	a-x.	$k_{(a)mol.} \times 10^{-4} \text{min.}^{-1}$						
45	291.5	2.96	291.0	2.29	171.0	2.46						
60	291.5	2.22	231.5	1.99	290.5	1.75	352.5	1.86	170.5	1.89		
75	287.5	1.95	230.0	1.69	290.5	1.4	350.0	1.58	166.0	1.87		
90	287.5	1.63	228.0	1.5	288.0	1.26	348.5	1.11	164.0	1.69	225.0	1.48
105	285.5	1.46	228.0	1.29	285.0	1.18	346.5	1.22	163.0	1.50	224.5	1.29
120	282.5	1.37	225.5	1.22	282.5	1.10	345.5	1.10			223.5	1.16
135			224.5	1.12	281.5	1.01					223.0	1.1
150											225.5	0.96
165											227.0	0.89

In the case of CO-H₂ mixture it is difficult to mark a sharp equilibrium point; the change is rapid in the first few minutes and proceeds on more gradually over a long duration. The progress of the change with increasing temperature, however, unlike as in the case of CO, is markedly retarded (Table II, columns 3 and 2, Fig. 3).

Fig. 2

DISCUSSION

The pressure reduction (self condensation) of CO is well explained by the fact that carbon suboxides and CO₂ are formed according to a change along the following lines (Brodie, Berthelot, Ott, Crespi and Lunt, *loc. cit.*):

No data, excepting one by Lunt and Mumford (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1711; cf. also *ibid.*, 1925, 2052) are available in the literature about the pressure variations by discharge in the above systems. The present work indicates a change which is never more than 17% reduction (vide Table I). From this it is clear that the above reaction(s) never proceeds to completion which would require a pressure change of 75% or more. It is suggested therefore that the reactions (decompositions) of CO are reversible. This view is supported by the fact that the steady state (equilibrium point) can be influenced by a change in temperature which probably alters the effective concentration of carbon suboxides (Table I, column 2).

The observation that the rate of reduction in pressure is rapid (vide Fig. 2) in the first few minutes, and later on slows down and tends towards uniformity suggests that the nature, and presumably, the order of the reaction in the first few minutes might be different from the one at the later stage. Carbon suboxides are the principal products of this reaction. They might arise in two ways: (1) by multiple collisions of CO molecules, and (2) by a stepwise building up from charged or excited CO molecules.

Since the probability of the former is very restricted in a gaseous system, the latter mechanism has been generally favoured (Lind, "The Chemical effects of alpha particles and electrons", The Chem. Catalog Co., New York, 1928; Mund, *Ann. Soc. Sci. Brux.*, 1931, B, 51, 1; 1934, 54, 30, Livingston, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1936, 48, 334). When subjected to electrical field CO might give rise to positive ions by ionisation which in their turn might associate with other neutral or excited molecules giving rise to loose aggregations, called 'clusters' (Caress and Rideal, *loc. cit.*), e.g.

and so on, which on neutralisation of their charge or/and dissociation due to further electron impact yield various suboxides and CO_2 :

The whole process may be akin to simple polymerisation, in this case brought about by electrical excitation of unsaturated CO molecules.

Thus, the reduction in pressure of CO may be attributed to two causes: (i) to a small extent due to the formation of slow moving ionic clusters, and (ii) largely because of the formation of solid carbon suboxides from the former. At higher gas pressures, because of the smaller mean free path, it may be expected that the rate of formation of these slow moving cluster ions would be more than the rate at which they dissociate into smaller fragments, viz. neutral oxides of carbon, with the result that the percentage fall in pressure would be less. A similar phenomenon has been observed by Holt (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 30) in the case of dry CO_2 .

A rise in temperature of the reaction vessel, according to general theories would bring about an augmented dissociation or/and decomposition of the cluster ions and consequent 'building-up' of high molecular weight structures, e.g., solids (*vide supra*). Therefore, it is to be anticipated that at higher temperature of CO, fall in pressure would be greater (Table I, columns 3 and 2) and the time required for reaching the equilibrium shorter (Table I, column 4).

It is difficult to assign quantitatively any mechanism, and therefore, the order to the reaction in the earlier stage. But the velocity constants, k , calculated according to the unimolecular expression reasonably point to the conclusion that in the later stages (near the equilibrium) it is unimolecular (Table IV). This probably suggests that it is only the transformation of carbon suboxides or clusters that predominates in the later stages. In the earlier stages the reaction cannot be represented as a simple mono- or bi-order process. This is to be expected on the mechanism suggested above.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

A mixture of CO and H₂, when subjected to silent electric discharge, is known to give a number of products viz. H.CHO, CO₂, CH₄, H₂O, CH₂OH.CHO, C₂H₄, etc.

The formation of these has been variously represented (Losanitsch, Löb, Wendt and Evans, Koenig and Wenig, *loc. cit.*):

As will be seen, excepting (1), all these changes are multi-order reactions and therefore have a very restricted possibility in a gaseous system.

The values of the velocity constant (vide Table III) calculated according to the bimolecular expression, show a remarkable constancy, except for one at a long exposure viz. 10 min, indicating that it is the change (1) which predominates. Work of the authors on the formation of H.CH(O) using large quantities of C(O) and H₂ also points to the same conclusion (unpublished data). Further it has also been shown that self-condensation of C(O) in presence of H₂ is not appreciable (Caress and Rideal, *loc. cit.* Sahasrabudhey and Deshpande, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1950, **31A**, 322). The large fall in pressure in the earlier stages of discharge (vide Fig. 3) may thus be attributed to the primary reaction (1).

The lower values of fall in pressure at higher temperatures of the reaction vessel (Table II, columns 3 and 2) may be explained in view of the adverse influence of temperature on the exothermic reaction

and also partly on the depolymerising action of temperature on the formaldehyde polymers. Further work is in progress.

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